

FUNCTIONAL UV COATING COMPOSITE FOR STEEL COATING

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ABSTRACT

Recently, considerable effort has focused on the functional coating of antibacterial properties in coated steel applications, and which seem to be quite useful in mobile devices, appliances, interior, buildings, and medical stuffs. For this, various bacteria-killing techniques have been developed, such as silver nanoparticles, layer-by-layer (LBL) nanofabrication, incorporation of various antibiotics, and so on. However, the antibacterial coating simultaneously keep up with other requirements like, anticorrosive, high gloss, suitable mechanical properties. In this work, we developed antibacterial coating formulation based on UV steel coating process by using chemically-modified urushiol lacquer. In fact, various kinds of lacquer trees (e.g., toxicodendron vernicifluum) have been used as paints and coating materials for woods and metal surfaces since 5,000 years in oriental culture. This natural lacquer exhibits superior barrier property against oxygen and water, as well as good durability, chemical resistance, and mechanical properties. However, traditional technique based on the enzymatic polymerization needs long time as well as manpower. In addition, pristine urushiol derivatives tend to inhibit free-radical polymerization due to its catechol structure of radical stabilization mechanism. Herein we present a facile method to minimize the radical inhibition for the development of antibacterial, anticorrosive, and high gloss UV coating formulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In oriental culture, various kinds of lacquer trees have been used as paints and coating materials for woods and metal surfaces since 5,000 years. This natural lacquer exhibits superior barrier property against oxygen and water, as well as good durability, chemical resistance, and mechanical properties.

The lacquer consists of urushiol derivatives (60-70%), water (~20%), other water or oil-soluble proteins, laccase, and gums (~10%). It has been well known that the urushiol derivatives bring out allergy and they can be easily purified from the lacquer by solvent extraction with various nonpolar or polar organic solvents. Physical properties are follows:

- Boiling point : 210~220 °C
- Appearance: Dark brown, viscous liquid
- Derivatives: Catechols having unsaturated alkyl chains

The raw urushiol volume could be contracted on the surface of films after coating.

The catechol group of urushiol could be dissociated to various semiquinone radicals under the UV irradiation. A single nonbonding electron of the semiquinone radical is delocalized to phenyl nucleus, stabilized by conjugated system.

Herein, we describe the chemical modification of urushiol with several mono-isocyanates to solve such as problems. The coating properties of urushiol/UV coating solution, such as antibacterial, anticorrosive, and thermo-mechanical properties also will be discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Extraction and chemical modification of pristine urushiol

200 mL raw lacquer was stirred in an open vessel (bottom diameter, 110 mm; capacity, 1000 mL) at room temperature for about 1.5 h, then be dissolved into 500 mL methylene chloride. After the

filtration (paper filter, 100 mm) we could get nearly 40 wt.% pristine urushiol (PU) from the raw lacquer.

The chemical modification of PU was carried out in 100 mL three-necked flask fitted with a condenser and a magnetic stirrer. Firstly, 2 mol PU and 15 mL THF were injected into the reactor in the presence of 3 wt.% SnOct2. Then, 1 mol BI or 0.14 mol TMI was added into the reactants mixture. The reaction was carried out for 2 hr at 40 oC under N2 atmosphere. Through the chemical modification of PU, we prepared three kinds of isocyanate-modified urushiols, i.e., hexyl isocyanate-modified urushiol (HI-MU), benzyl isocyanate-modified urushiol (BI-MU), and TMI-modified urushiol (TMI-MU). After modification and volatilization of THF we could get 90 wt.% MU. The reaction is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Chemical modification of urushiol with mono-isocyanates

2.2 Preparation of UV Coating Solutions and Their Film

In order to prepare UV coating solutions, simple blending technique was used. In the case of 10 wt.% HI-MU containing UV coating solution, for example, 1 g HI-MU, BI-MU and TMI-MU. 8.7 g UV coating solution, and 0.3 g PI were mixed together and stirred. We prepared three kinds of blended UV coating solution from HI, BI, and TMI-MUs with 10 wt.%.

For the film formation, we used a tailor made UV coating chamber with a high pressure mercury lamp (RX-H1000-2/Drawer, 170-210 W/cm², RAYNICS) in atmospheric conditions. These prepolymers of modification spread on two different substrates (steel plate and glass) and cured using UV light to polymerize and obtain 5±0.5 μm constant thickness film and 300 ±10 μm free-standing film.

2.3 Characterization

Infrared spectra of pristine urushiol and chemical modification of urushiol was measured using a FTIR spectrometer (Impact 400D, Nicolet, Madison, WI) in the wavenumber of 400 ~ 4000 cm⁻¹ at room temperature. For each IR spectrometer sample, 32 scans at a 4 cm⁻¹ resolution were collected in the transmittance mode.

The chemical structure of pristine urushiol and chemical modification of urushiol synthesized in this study was analyzed using ¹H NMR and FT-IR spectrometers. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained on a 300MHz FT-NMR, which was operated at 300MHz using DMSO as a solvent. Infrared spectra were obtained with the computerized Nicolet Impact 400D Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer. For each sample, 32 scans at 2 cm⁻¹ resolution were collected in transmittance mode.

The changes in the chemical structure of Urushiol/UV coating film surfaces were analyzed by

electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis (ESCA: Model ESCA 250). The ESCA was equipped with AlK radiation source at 1486.6 eV and 300 W at the anode. Survey scan and carbon 1S core level scan spectra were taken to analyze the film surfaces.

Antibacterial analysis was tested with cells of bacteria according to JIS Z 2801 at 37±1 °C for 24 h. Cell types are Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC6538P, S. aureus) and Escherichia coli (ATCC8739, E. coli). Antimicrobial activity (R) was calculated according to equation:

$$R = \log \left(\frac{B}{A} \right) - \log \left(\frac{C}{A} \right) = \log \left(\frac{B}{C} \right)$$

where A is the average number of viable cells of bacteria immediately after inoculation on the control (untreated) sample, B, the average number of viable cells of bacteria on the control sample after 24 h, and C is the average number of viable cells of bacteria on the Urushiol/UV coating samples after 24 h.

2.4 Salt Spray Test

Urushiol/UV coating samples were applied onto the electro-galvanized steel plates (150mm×75mm) with a bar coater and dried in a convective oven at 80 °C for 12 h.

The average thickness of coating layer was 5±0.5μm.

The steel plates were wetted by spraying with a 5 wt.% aq. NaCl solution for 24, 48, and 72 hrs at ambient conditions.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the FT-IR spectrum of pristine urushiol prepared here. The pristine urushiol was identified by the characteristic IR peaks, such as O-H stretching vibration peak near 3600-3200 cm⁻¹, -C-O stretching band at 1250 cm⁻¹ and 1050 cm⁻¹, C=C stretching band at 1600 and 1475 cm⁻¹, and the C=O group near 1730 cm⁻¹.

Figure 1: FT-IR spectrum of pristine urushiol

FT-IR spectrum of chemical modification of urushiol are shown in Figure 2. Pristine urushiol of OH absorption in the 3600-3200 cm⁻¹ before chemical modification. After that, no OH peak was observed and the secondary NH peaks around 3200-3000 cm⁻¹ were found in HI-MU and BI-MU samples. The NCO peak at 2270 cm⁻¹ from the mono-isocyanates (HI, BI and TMI) substantially disappeared after the completion of reaction. The structure of chemical modification of urushiol synthesized in this chapter was identified from these characteristic peaks.

Figure 2: FT-IR spectrum of chemical modification of urushiol

The ^1H NMR spectra of the chemical modification of urushiol were presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: ^1H NMR spectra of chemical modification of urushiol

$^1\text{HNMR}$ spectrum of HI-MU. H^a $\delta=3.6-3.7$, H^b $\delta=1.5$, H^c $\delta=1.3$, H^d $\delta=0.9$, H^e $\delta=6.6-6.7$.

$^1\text{HNMR}$ spectrum of BI-MU. H^a $\delta=7.3$, H^b $\delta=4.2$, H^c $\delta=6.6$.

$^1\text{HNMR}$ spectrum of TMI-MU. H^a $\delta=4.9$ and 5.1 , H^b $\delta=1.06$, H^c $\delta=1.27$, H^d $\delta=6.9$, H^e $\delta=7.2-7.3$

Figure 4 shows the effect of gel contents on the polymerization time. 10 wt.% MU were purified to determine the amounts of polymer by dissolving them in acetone. The unreacted monomer and homopolymer of MU were dissolved in acetone. The precipitate obtained was washed several times with acetone and dried in a vacuum oven until a constant weight was obtained. The gel contents of MU were gradually increased when the polymerization time was extended until completely finished.

Figure 4: The effect of gel contents on the polymerization time

The antibacterial property of the films was analyzed according to JIS Z 2801 (at 37±1 °C for 24 h). In the analysis, UV, PU, 10 wt.% HI-MU, BI-MU and TMI-MU were tested with Escherichia coli (ATCC8739, E. coli). The cell suspension of E. coli (3.7×10⁵ CFU/mL) was prepared in the nutrient broth. An aliquot (0.4mL of inoculum) was then placed onto at least three replicate sub-samples per species of the treated surface (50mm×50mm, sterilized PU, 3 films by UV) under test and several replicate subsamples per species of the untreated surface (50mm×50mm, sterilized control films by UV) and held in intimate contact using a sterile steel film (40mm×40 mm).

The detailed methods for antibacterial analysis of the chemical modification of urushiol prepared in this study are summarized in Table 1.

Test Item	Assessment of Antibacterial Activity
Test Method	JIS Z 2801(2000)
Test Result	Bacteriostatic reduction value; R
Type of sample & Size	Metal, 50×50mm
Bacteriostatic reduction value; $R = \log(B/C)$	B : The number of bacteria on the control samples after 24h C : The number of bacteria on the test sample after 24h

Table 1: This is the example of a table.

The platelet adhesion (%) results for control, pristine urushiol and the chemical modification of urushiol films are shown in Figure 5 and 6. As expected, the highest adhesion was observed on the control UV coating surface and urushiol component affected significantly to cells of bacteria detachment. The cells of bacteria decreased markedly with chemical modification of urushiol. These results seem to be related to the antibacterial properties of the urushiol. It was also demonstrated that the number of cells of bacteria significantly reduced when urushiol was modified by TMI. From these results, it was found that the chemical modification of urushiol films are much more resistant to cells of bacteria adhesion compared with the control UV coating sample.

Figure 5: The antibacterial property of control, pristine urushiol and the chemical modification of urushiol films

Figure 6: The Antimicrobial activity (R) of control, pristine urushiol and the chemical modification of urushiol films

9 CONCLUSIONS

Modified urushiols were successfully synthesized and their properties of films were investigated with 10 wt.% concentration of the modified urushiol. The gel contents of the modified urushiol were gradually increased as the polymerization time increased. 10 wt.% modified urushiol films showed better inhibitory results on the growth of bacteria than unmodified urushiol/UV or pristine UV coating films.